

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D6.11 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 2

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

Contact Email: contact@up2030-he.eu

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Contributor(s)				
Reviewer(s)	Constanza Vera (USTUTT), Salma Shrestha (Fraunhofer), Tommaso Bassetti (ICA)			
Abstract	The D6.11 — Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 2 is the final report on the ways in which UP2030 worked with related and sister projects to enhance impact, as well as with broader initiatives like the EU Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities.			

Document History

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Executive summary

Deliverable 6.11 (D6.11) Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 2 presents the final overview of UP2030’s collaboration and synergy efforts with other Mission-related projects and initiatives under the EU Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. Building on D6.10 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1, this deliverable documents the implementation, achievements, and outcomes of the clustering work carried out throughout the project.

The activities were structured around two levels of engagement: a Core Cluster (Urban Planning and Design Cluster), involving UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value, and a broader Exchange Cluster, engaging with the NetZeroCities (NZC), Mission Platform, the Cities Mission Secretariat, and related initiatives such as the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and the Smart Cities Marketplace.

This document highlights the joint actions implemented to strengthen collaboration, including regular coordination meetings, shared participation in Mission events, joint dissemination and communication campaigns and cross-project learning exchanges. These efforts enhanced the visibility, coherence, and impact of the projects while fostering alignment within the Mission.

Finally, the deliverable outlines the legacy and future prospects of the collaboration, showing how the established structures, communication channels, and partnerships will continue to support knowledge exchange, exploitation, and sustained cooperation beyond UP2030’s lifetime.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work packages structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with ICLEI Europe, Fraunhofer, Work Package (WP) 6, and relevant projects CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
Roadmap: Collaboration with the Mission and related projects (internal operational document)	D6.5 – Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 3 D6.12 – Sharing UP2030 best practices and policy briefs with the Mission’s platform
D6.8 – Exploitation & Sustainability Planning & Activities Report 1	
D6.10 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1	
Mil.2: Launch of UP2030 visual identification and virtual presence, and initial D&C plan	

The target audiences for this deliverable are UP2030 project partners, as well as relevant project consortia and pilots/followers, e.g., sister projects CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value. Further audiences include NZC, the Cities Mission Secretariat and stakeholders involved in the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. The main beneficiaries of this content are partners and cities seeking to build on the collaboration models, dissemination practices, and lessons learned from the clustering work carried out during UP2030. As this deliverable marks the final stage of these activities, it supports partners and sister projects in consolidating and transferring results for wider visibility and long-term

uptake. Once finalised, the document will be shared within the consortium and with the sister projects and made publicly available on [Zenodo](#) and [CORDIS](#).

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
D	Deliverable
EURESFO	European Urban Resilience Forum
Mil	Milestone
NZC	NetZeroCities
PO	Project Officer
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

D6.11 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 2 presents the second and final report on clustering and synergy activities carried out under UP2030. It builds upon and updates [D6.10 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1](#), providing an overview of the actions implemented during the final phase of the project to reinforce collaboration and knowledge exchange with related Horizon Europe projects and initiatives under the EU Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities.

This deliverable documents the activities undertaken jointly with the sister projects CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value, as well as interactions with the Mission Platform and other initiatives. These collaborations aimed to create synergies, maximise the visibility and impact of Mission-related outcomes, and strengthen alignment across projects supporting cities in their transition towards climate neutrality.

It summarises the key outcomes, including joint participation in major Mission events, collaborative dissemination efforts, co-organised knowledge exchange sessions and coordination on shared thematic priorities relevant to urban transition processes. It also provides a consolidated overview of lessons learned, good practices and recommendations for maintaining and expanding these collaborative mechanisms beyond the lifetime of UP2030. The overall goal is to ensure that the networks, tools, and strategies developed through this cooperation remain accessible, transferable, and beneficial to the broader Mission community of cities and stakeholders.

1.2 Document structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ **Section 1 – Introduction:** Description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure
- ❖ **Section 2 – Objectives of clustering activities with other Mission initiatives:** Outline of the main objectives guiding UP2030's collaboration with related Mission projects and initiatives, highlighting the rationale for joint actions and expected benefits.
- ❖ **Section 3 – Clustering activities:** Overview of the collaborative actions undertaken throughout the project, summarising the outcomes and added value generated through these synergies.
- ❖ **Section 4 – Future synergies/legacy:** Discussion of perspectives for maintaining and further developing cooperation beyond the lifetime of UP2030, ensuring that the networks and outputs created remain accessible to the broader Mission community.
- ❖ **Section 5 – Conclusions:** Closing reflections on the relevance and impact of clustering activities in enhancing the coherence, visibility, and legacy of Mission-related projects.

2 Objectives of clustering activities with other Mission initiatives

UP2030 aimed to collaborate with other related projects and Mission initiatives to enhance impact, avoid duplication of efforts, improve outreach to target audiences, and jointly contribute to the broader goals of the EU Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. These goals were established under the framework of collaboration with other Mission projects, as defined in the UP2030 Grant Agreement (2022), which included the commitment to “build synergies between UP2030 and other Mission initiatives and projects to enhance dissemination range and impact on the wider end-user community, as well as accelerate cities’ progress.” The synergies developed under this objective included the identification of transversal themes across related projects and initiatives, the organisation of joint dissemination activities and the facilitation of knowledge exchange.

To this end, UP2030 partners (primarily ICLEI Europe and Fraunhofer) refined these objectives into two main areas that guided the clustering activities:

1. Enhancing dissemination impact and defining transversal themes, and
2. Raising awareness and strengthening the visibility and contribution of the projects within the Cities Mission framework.

These priorities were captured in a dynamic working document shared, and periodically reviewed, with the related projects (CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value), titled *Roadmap: Collaboration with the Mission and related projects*. The roadmap served as a practical coordination tool and remained the basis for planning and monitoring collaboration throughout the project. It outlined the shared plans for clustering and cooperation activities among the three Core Cluster projects and extended to interactions with NetZeroCities (NZN) and the Mission Platform, the Cities Mission Secretariat, and other relevant initiatives, such as the Smart Cities Marketplace and Scalable Cities.

2.1 Roadmap for collaboration

As described in D6.10 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1, UP2030 developed an internal, operationally focused roadmap under Task 6.4: “Collaboration with the Mission and related projects.” This roadmap defined the initial concept and structure for coordination, organised around two levels of engagement: A “Core Cluster,” with CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value projects; and a broader “Exchange Cluster” with NZN, the Cities Mission Secretariat and the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, alongside initiatives like the Smart Cities Marketplace and Scalable Cities. These two clusters have been conceptualised with different key aims and different key activities, elaborated in Sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2 below (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Core (in green) and Exchange Clusters (in purple) for Collaboration

In D6.10 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1, the roadmap served to establish shared objectives, identify areas of thematic alignment, and define the initial collaboration mechanisms. During the early phase of collaboration, broader coordination meetings involving both Core and Exchange Cluster partners supported the development of this shared framework. Since D6.10 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1, the collaboration evolved. Coordination became more streamlined and continued primarily within the Core Cluster, ensuring regular exchanges between UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, and Re-Value. The Exchange Cluster continued to be informed of relevant outcomes and opportunities through established communication channels, maintaining alignment with Mission-wide activities (see table below and Section 3.1 for further details).

Table 1: Overview of meetings of related projects and initiatives throughout UP2030 duration (M1-M36)

Meetings	Attendees
<p>Cluster Coordination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> February 2023 March 2023 June 2023 January 2024 June 2024 ((European Urban Resilience Forum(EURESFO)) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UP2030 CLIMABOROUGH Re-Value partners CINEA Mission Secretariat (only for February 2023) NZC (only for February 2023)
<p>Core Cluster</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> May 2024 June 2024 November 2024 January 2025 February 2025 (two meetings) March 2025 April 2025 (three meetings) May 2025 June 2025 July 2025 September 2025 October 2025 November 2025 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core Cluster <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication and Dissemination working group Knowledge Generation and Exchange working group Exchange Cluster on ad hoc basis, depending on Core Cluster meeting topics

In terms of longevity and legacy, UP2030 successfully initiated this collaboration through the development and implementation of the roadmap, which provided a clear structure for coordination and joint action among the cluster projects. The collaboration framework UP2030 helped establish is expected to continue through partners active in related initiatives (e.g., ICLEI Europe, which is also involved in Re-Value, will be able to carry and further build on the established connections). The structures and communication channels developed during the project can continue to be used to support knowledge sharing and interaction, including through dedicated groups and collaborative spaces created on platforms such as the Mission Platform.

2.1.1 Core Cluster

The identified Core Cluster, which took the leading role in the implementation of the clustering activities, included the consortium members of the three Mission Projects (UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, and Re-Value), as well as involved cities. As shown in Table 2, for this cluster, the objective was twofold: i) enhance dissemination and maximise impact for the project outcomes for the cities, and ii) identify cross-cutting themes across the three Mission Projects.

Table 2: Core Cluster overview

Involvement	Objectives
UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, Re-Value, cities involved in these projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance dissemination and maximise impact for the project outcomes for the cities, and Identify cross-cutting themes across the three Mission Projects

This collaboration took the form of:

- Building synergies among the Core Cluster and with the other groups of stakeholders (Exchange Cluster)
- Collaborating on dissemination and visibility actions
- Identifying cross-cutting themes and approaches between cluster projects
- Fostering exchange and mutual learning among cities
- Exploring opportunities for joint outputs (e.g., shared event contributions)

The collaboration within the Core Cluster began with the joint development of the roadmap, which was reviewed jointly with CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value to define an action plan.

Throughout the project, the Core Cluster maintained consistent coordination, meeting regularly to plan joint activities, align dissemination efforts, and share experiences among cities. To maximise the impact of project outcomes on cities, the collaboration also promoted engagement with other stakeholders from the Cities Mission. As the primary audience of this work was Mission and non-Mission cities, efforts were made to reach wider audiences through shared communication channels, participation in common events and collaboration with initiatives connected to the NZC and the broader Exchange Cluster (see Figure 2 below). Specific activities and measures to reach these audiences are described in Section 3.2 below.

Figure 2: Objectives of the Core Cluster (in green) and Exchange Cluster (in purple)

2.1.2 Exchange Cluster

The Exchange Cluster extended the scope of clustering activities beyond the Core Cluster to include the NZC Mission Platform, the Cities Mission Secretariat, the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and other related initiatives such as the Smart Cities Marketplace and Scalable Cities Initiative, as presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Exchange Cluster overview

Involvement	Objectives
UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, Re-Value alongside EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and associated projects, Relevant Initiatives, Cities Mission Secretariat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify opportunities and channels/events for joint dissemination alongside Cities Mission, NZC and related Mission projects Survey key project milestones suited to joint dissemination and create dissemination packages to be shared with Exchange Cluster members

During the early phase of UP2030, engagement with these initiatives focused on identifying opportunities for collaboration and joint dissemination, particularly around major Mission events and communication channels. These exchanges helped ensure that the activities of the Core Cluster were visible and aligned with the broader Mission ecosystem.

As the collaboration evolved, coordination within the Exchange Cluster became more targeted and primarily took place through existing communication channels and events, such as the Cities Mission Conference and interactions with the NZC team. This approach allowed the Core Cluster to maintain efficiency while keeping the Exchange Cluster informed of key outcomes and opportunities for synergy.

3 Clustering activities

3.1 Clustering activities with Core Cluster

3.1.1 Interactions undertaken

The Core Cluster built upon the initial series of exchange meetings facilitated by the Project Officer (PO), which laid the groundwork for structured collaboration among the three Mission projects (UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, and Re-Value). As reported in D6.10 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1, these PO-supported clustering meetings took place in February 2023, March 2023, June 2023, January 2024, and June 2024. They were essential in establishing a common understanding of the Mission context, identifying areas of thematic overlap, and agreeing on an initial roadmap for collaboration.

Building on these exchanges, the three projects transitioned into a more structured collaboration framework from late 2024 onward, formalising the Core Cluster as a standing coordination mechanism. Meetings were held regularly throughout 2024 and 2025, roughly every month, and became the main vehicle for planning, monitoring, and reporting on joint actions. This regular interaction allowed partners to synchronise dissemination activities, coordinate participation in Mission events, and share lessons from city-level implementation.

Early discussions also led to the drafting of the roadmap for collaboration, which became the central coordination tool for the cluster. Two thematic working groups were initially proposed: one on Knowledge Generation and Exchange and another on Communication and Dissemination. However, as collaboration intensified, it was collectively agreed that these topics could be effectively addressed through the regular cluster meetings without the need for separate groups. This approach proved more efficient, ensuring that all partners remained involved in key discussions and decisions.

The roadmap was jointly updated in May 2024, ahead of the in-person coordination meeting in Valencia (June 2024), which defined the next steps and action points leading into 2025. At that stage, the cluster also began preparing for major joint presences at Mission events and conferences, focusing on shared visibility and knowledge exchange opportunities.

By the end of the project, the Core Cluster had established itself as a well-coordinated and productive partnership, maintaining a strong rhythm of communication and ensuring alignment between the three projects' dissemination, capacity-building, and knowledge-sharing activities.

3.1.2 Activities implemented

Following the establishment of the Core Cluster structure, as aforementioned, the regular coordination meetings throughout 2024 and 2025 served to plan and implement joint activities, while allowing partners to review progress, coordinate event participation and align dissemination outputs.

The Core Cluster did not adopt a rotating co-chair system as initially proposed. Instead, coordination was carried out jointly, with ICLEI Europe and Fraunhofer supporting facilitation on behalf of UP2030. This pragmatic approach proved effective in maintaining momentum and inclusiveness across partners.

Joint events and presence at major conferences

Joint participation had already begun during the early stages of the collaboration, as reported in D6.10 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1. Nevertheless, the Core Cluster's joint visibility reached a peak in 2025, with coordinated participation in major Mission and EU urban transition events. These included:

- **Cities Mission Conference (Vilnius, May 2025):** In preparation for the Cities Mission Conference, the Core Cluster developed a joint concept for an Urban Planning and Design Pavilion, initially proposed by Re-Value and shaped collaboratively by UP2030 and CLIMABOROUGH. The Pavilion was envisioned as an interactive space to showcase results and tools from the three projects, including installations, short films, and city-led discussions. However, due to space and conference format constraints, the Pavilion could not be realised as a separate exhibition area.

Instead, the Core Cluster successfully adapted the concept into a shared exhibition stand and joint Marketplace presence, maintaining the Pavilion’s original purpose of demonstrating the collective contribution of the three projects to urban planning and design for climate-neutral transitions.

The joint stand featured interactive elements such as UP2030’s card game and Re-Value’s Impact Model Dominoes, along with videos, city stories, and printed materials from all three projects. The conference gathered around 825 participants overall and engagement at the stand was active throughout the event. Approximately 800 cluster postcards were distributed and around 65 participants interacted directly through the games and demonstrations. In addition, 55 participants attended the Urban Planning and Design World Café session, which created space for discussion on planning approaches, city experiences and lessons learned across the three projects.

The activity served as a visible showcase of cooperation within the Cities Mission ecosystem and offered valuable lessons for future joint event planning and coordinated dissemination.

- **UP2030 Final Event (Barcelona, November 2025):** The final event served as both the culmination of UP2030’s activities and a flagship dissemination opportunity for the cluster. CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value contributed to plenary discussions and parallel sessions, sharing cities experiences, and insights on lessons learned in supporting climate-neutral urban transitions. Communication materials were prepared and shared through newsletters and social media campaigns. The event also helped reinforce the visibility of all three projects within the Cities Mission community and marked a symbolic handover of collaboration to continue beyond the project’s formal end.

Knowledge exchange and capacity building

The Core Cluster effectively integrated its partners’ existing capacity-building structures into a shared learning environment:

- **Re-Value Rounds:** UP2030 and CLIMABOROUGH partners and cities regularly participated in Re-Value’s recurring knowledge-sharing sessions, including the January, March, and May 2025 rounds. These sessions focused on topics such as sustainable mobility, barriers to innovation and impact pathways.
- **CLIMABOROUGH webinars:** UP2030 and Re-Value representatives joined the April 2025 webinar on innovative procurement for climate transition.
- **UP2030 webinars:** The Core Cluster partners were invited to participate in two UP2030-led webinars: “The Data-Driven City: Finding the Balance Between Innovation and Privacy” (May 2025) and “Ethical Dimensions within Horizon Europe Projects” (October 2025); which fostered discussions on data governance, ethics, and citizen engagement.

These interactions deepened cross-project learning and demonstrated the complementarity of the projects’ approaches to city transition, governance, and stakeholder engagement.

Joint dissemination and communication

The Core Cluster placed strong emphasis on joint communication and dissemination throughout the project, ensuring that the activities and outcomes of each partner project were visible under a shared identity. All three projects coordinated closely to align messaging, plan joint visibility efforts, and promote cluster activities across multiple channels.

Joint dissemination materials were prepared for major events such as the Cities Mission Conference and the UP2030 Final Event, including shared postcards, banners, videos, and reading corner materials that highlighted the complementary focus of the three projects. A shared visual identity was adopted at the events, helping to present the Core Cluster as a cohesive and recognisable collaboration within the Cities Mission framework.

Cross-promotion took place regularly through the projects' newsletters and social media channels. Announcements and updates about joint activities were featured in the UP2030 newsletter (~230 subscribers), CLIMABOROUGH newsletter (~650 subscribers) as well as in the Informed Cities newsletter (~1.500 subscribers), which is led by Re-Value. Through this coordination, updates on cluster events, webinars, and publications reached a broad audience across the Mission community and beyond. The projects also supported one another's communication efforts by sharing news, invitations, and event highlights through their respective online platforms, expanding the visibility, and impact of their outputs.

In addition to external dissemination, the cluster maintained open and regular internal communication through shared folders, collaborative planning documents, and frequent online coordination meetings. This ensured transparency, consistency of messaging, and timely exchange of information across the projects.

Overall, the joint dissemination and communication activities helped strengthen the collective visibility of the Core Cluster, ensuring that the results of the three projects reached a broader audience of Mission and non-Mission cities, practitioners, and policymakers. This coordinated approach also laid the groundwork for sustained collaboration and knowledge sharing beyond the lifetime of UP2030 (see Section 4 for further details).

Coordination and outcomes

Over the project, the Core Cluster demonstrated that regular coordination could be highly effective. The decision not to formalise working groups allowed the cluster to remain flexible and responsive, ensuring that actions were jointly developed and agreed during the coordination meetings.

This structure led to tangible results:

- Enhanced visibility of all three projects under a shared identity at EU and Mission events;
- Increased cross-project participation in knowledge-sharing activities;
- More coherent communication and dissemination outputs; and
- A foundation for continued cooperation through shared channels such as the Mission Platform.

Overall, the Core Cluster matured into a cohesive and productive collaboration framework. Through consistent coordination, shared communication, and joint visibility, UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, and Re-Value demonstrated the added value of clustering within the Mission ecosystem, contributing to stronger alignment, wider outreach and more integrated support for European cities on their paths to climate neutrality.

Table 4 summarises the main coordination actions, meetings, and joint activities carried out by the Core Cluster throughout the project. It highlights how UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, and Re-Value collaborated to strengthen alignment and visibility within the Cities Mission.

Table 4: Overview of Core Cluster activities – Summary of actions and outputs throughout UP2030 duration

Area	Core Cluster: Actions and outputs
Within Core Cluster	
Regular coordination meetings	Regular online Core Cluster meetings were held periodically, roughly every month, to align activities, plan events, and monitor progress.
Update of collaboration roadmap	The <i>Roadmap: Collaboration with the Mission and related projects</i> was jointly updated in May 2024 and used throughout 2025 to guide coordination and planning.
Joint event participation	Coordinated joint participation at major Mission events, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EURESFO 2023 (Cascais) – Joint session on climate-neutral and resilient cities. • EURESFO 2024 (Valencia) – Shared Marketplace stand as Urban Planning and Design Cluster. • Cities Mission Conference 2025 (Vilnius) – Joint stand and World Café session (~55 participants). • UP2030 Final Event 2025 (Barcelona) – Joint sessions and shared dissemination materials.
Urban Planning and Design Pavilion concept	The Core Cluster jointly developed the concept for an Urban Planning and Design Pavilion for the Vilnius Conference. Due to space and format constraints, this was adapted into a shared exhibition stand and Marketplace presence.
Community of Practice/Knowledge Exchange	Participation of partner cities across learning activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Re-Value Rounds (Jan, Mar, May 2025) • CLIMABOROUGH Webinars (Apr 2025) • UP2030 Webinars (May and Oct 2025)
Cross-promotion and communication	Joint visibility and promotion, including updates, featured through UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, and Re-Value social media channels and newsletters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UP2030 (~230 subscribers) • CLIMABOROUGH (~650 subscribers) • Re-Value (~1500 subscribers)
Joint dissemination materials	Creation of co-branded dissemination materials: postcards (~800 distributed in Vilnius), banners, and reading corner materials shared at joint events.
Coordination model	Initially proposed working groups were replaced by a more flexible approach based on regular coordination meetings, ensuring efficiency and inclusiveness.
Interaction with Exchange Cluster	
Engagement with Mission Platform (NZC)	The Core Cluster maintained regular contact with the NZC and the Cities Mission Secretariat, informing them of collaboration outcomes and joint activities.
Dissemination via Mission channels	Shared project outputs and updates through the NZC communication spaces and discussions on future resource visibility via the Mission Platform.
Collaboration with related initiatives	Periodic exchanges and alignment with other Mission-related initiatives, including the Mission on Adaptation to

	Climate Change, Smart Cities Marketplace and Scalable Cities Initiative.
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3.2 Clustering activities with Exchange Cluster

3.2.1 Interactions undertaken

The Exchange Cluster extended the collaboration beyond the Core Cluster to include the NZC Mission Platform, the Cities Mission Secretariat and other relevant initiatives such as the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, the Smart Cities Marketplace, and the Scalable Cities Initiative.

Building on the activities previously reported in D6.10 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1, UP2030 engaged in additional joint interactions through events organised under these initiatives, such as the Smart City Expo World Congress & Smart Cities Marketplace Forum 2025 (Barcelona, November 2025).

These joint presence helped foster collaboration, strengthen visibility, and promote the collective contribution of the cluster to urban sustainability and innovation within the Cities Mission ecosystem.

3.2.2 Activities implemented

Joint dissemination efforts were carried out in close coordination with the Cities Mission and the Mission Platform. Throughout the project, UP2030 and its partners identified relevant opportunities and channels to share project updates and results with the wider Mission community.

Dissemination opportunities were identified through ongoing coordination meetings and exchanges with the NZC and the Mission Secretariat. Project milestones and key achievements were promoted through joint communication activities, including newsletters, event visibility and participation in Mission conferences.

To support this process, partners shared key project tools, resources and knowledge outputs through Mission-related channels and events. Results from UP2030 were made visible via the Mission Platform, ensuring that cities and stakeholders across related initiatives had access to project resources. The detailed description of this process and the materials shared is presented in D6.12 – Sharing UP2030 best practices and policy briefs with the Mission’s platform. While the initial roadmap had foreseen the creation of formal “dissemination packages,” it was instead chosen to share key tools, resources, and results directly through Mission-related channels and events, achieving the same purpose in a more flexible format.

These efforts strengthened alignment between UP2030 and the broader Mission ecosystem and increased awareness of the results and experiences emerging from the project.

Table 5 summarises the main coordination actions, meetings, and outputs related to the Exchange Cluster. It highlights how UP2030 collaborated with the Mission and other related initiatives to share results, align activities and strengthen visibility within the wider Cities Mission ecosystem.

Table 5: Overview of Exchange Cluster activities – Summary of all actions and outputs throughout UP2030 duration

Area	Exchange Cluster: Actions and outputs
Mission and EU Events	Participation in major Mission and EU events, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NZC Annual Conference 2023 (Brussels) • Smart City Expo World Congress & Smart Cities Marketplace Forum 2023 (Barcelona) • NZC Annual Conference 2024 (Valencia)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart City Expo World Congress & Smart Cities Marketplace Forum 2025 (Barcelona)
Marketplace presence	Common presence at Marketplace areas during these events, showcasing project results and highlighting upcoming activities and initiatives to strengthen collaboration and visibility.
Coordination with Mission Platform	Regular communication and information exchange with the Mission Platform and the Cities Mission Secretariat to ensure alignment between cluster activities and the wider Mission framework.
Sharing of updates and outputs	Project updates and outcomes were shared and discussions took place with the Mission Platform on visibility opportunities.
Dissemination materials	Sharing of tools, resources and results from UP2030 through Mission-related channels and events, including the Mission Platform and Cities Mission conferences.
Collaboration with related initiatives	Alignment and informal exchanges with related EU initiatives, including the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, Smart Cities Marketplace, and Scalable Cities Initiative.

3.3 Documentation of activities

All activities carried out under the clustering framework were systematically documented to ensure transparency and traceability. Records of meetings, joint planning sessions, and collaborative actions were maintained throughout the project, following the principles set out in the UP2030 Data Management Plan (UP2030 Project, 2022).

A shared rolling document was used to register the Core Cluster meetings, including detailed minutes, assigned tasks, and next steps. These records were stored in the project’s SharePoint repository, ensuring accessibility for all partners.

For collaborative activities and exchanges, interactive digital tools were used to facilitate participatory work and record outcomes. Screenshots, images, and results from these sessions were collected and archived within the same repository. This approach ensured that all relevant data, materials, and decisions related to the clustering process could be traced and referenced after the project’s completion.

4 Future synergies/legacy

The collaboration established between UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, and Re-Value has created a strong foundation for continued cooperation beyond the project's lifetime. The working relationships and shared communication channels developed through UP2030 have proven the value of coordinated action among Mission projects and are expected to remain active in various forms.

Although UP2030 has concluded, its partners remain engaged with the Missions through other ongoing initiatives. ICLEI Europe, which also leads communication in Re-Value, will continue to support exchanges within the Core Cluster, ensuring that the connections and visibility achieved are maintained. Other partners involved in both projects are likewise well positioned to continue the dialogue and build on the methods and tools developed through the clustering work.

The collaboration will also serve as a reference point for future participation in Mission events and the sharing of results through the Mission Platform, which hosts selected UP2030 deliverables and knowledge products. This ensures that the insights and tools produced remain accessible to Mission and non-Mission cities across Europe.

Beyond the formal Mission structure, the cooperation fostered among the three projects is expected to continue informally through existing communication channels such as newsletters, social media, and follow-up meetings. The sister projects have also expressed interest in maintaining collaboration through joint contributions to webinars, event sessions, thematic discussions, and possible participation of UP2030 partners in their final events.

The continuation of these collaborative links also contributes directly to UP2030's exploitation and sustainability strategy (as outlined in D6.8 – Exploitation & Sustainability Planning & Activities Report 1). By keeping results visible through the Mission Platform and related channels, the clustering work supports the long-term uptake and reuse of project outcomes. The ongoing cooperation among partners will enable further joint research, policy engagement, and integration of UP2030 results into future initiatives, ensuring a lasting impact beyond the project's lifetime.

5 Conclusions

This document provides an overview of the clustering activities carried out under UP2030. Building on the initial framework established in D6.10 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1, this deliverable captures the implementation and results of the collaboration between projects and Mission initiatives. The clustering activities were structured across two levels: a Core Cluster, formed by UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, and Re-Value; and a broader Exchange Cluster, which included the NZC, the Mission Platform, the Cities Mission Secretariat and related initiatives such as the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and the Smart Cities Marketplace.

The activities carried out successfully achieved the two key objectives originally defined: (1) enhancing dissemination impact and identifying cross-cutting topics across the three Mission projects; and (2) raising awareness and strengthening the collective contribution of the projects within the Cities Mission.

Over the course of the project, these objectives were accomplished through regular coordination meetings, joint participation at major Mission events, cross-project learning activities, and coordinated dissemination efforts. The Core Cluster collaboration resulted in a visible and coherent presence at the Cities Mission Conference 2025 and the UP2030 Final Event, while continuous communication ensured alignment with the broader Mission community.

The clustering experience highlights several lessons for future Horizon Europe Mission-driven projects. Early and consistent coordination across projects can significantly improve alignment of communication and ensure more strategic engagement with Mission initiatives such as NZC. The involvement of cities in joint activities proved valuable but also demonstrated that cities benefit most when exchanges are structured, predictable, and clearly linked to their own transition needs. Providing targeted opportunities for city-to-city learning, especially for cities engaged in both the Cities Mission and the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, can help them use available platforms more effectively. Finally, shared visibility at Mission events emerged as an efficient way to amplify collective impact and could be expanded in future initiatives to reinforce coherence across Mission-related projects.

In conclusion, the clustering work under UP2030 has proven to be an effective approach for increasing the collective outreach and influence of the participating projects. The relationships, tools and methods established will continue to support cooperation and knowledge sharing beyond the end of the project, contributing to the ongoing legacy of the EU Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities.

6 References

UP2030 Project. (2022) Grant Agreement. Unpublished confidential document

7 Annex I: Roadmap – Collaboration with the Mission and related projects

7.1 Introduction

This roadmap is a guiding document to initiate and strengthen the collaboration between the Cities Mission, NetZeroCities (NZN) and the related Mission projects (UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value). ICLEI, as partner of the UP2030 project, has developed this document to outline the main objectives and the key activities to achieve cross sectorial collaboration among the above-mentioned projects and initiatives of the Cities Mission. The target audiences of this document are the organisations, researchers, and city members of the consortia of the Mission Projects, from this point onward referred to as core stakeholders.

This roadmap focuses on **creating two working groups** focused on key areas of collaboration:

1. Enhance dissemination impact and define cross-cutting themes
2. Raise awareness/impact of the projects to the Cities Mission

In the following sections of this document the key objectives are further detailed. The clustering of the core stakeholders as well as the most appropriate methods of engagement with them will be co-developed in upcoming meetings with the Mission Projects. Overall, the roadmap adopts an approach of identifying the purpose of engagement (why), the main stakeholders to be engaged with the respective themes (who), and the most appropriate methods for their engagement (how).

7.2 What is the objective of the roadmap?

This document has identified two main areas of collaboration, as mentioned above, the objectives of which are: to boost impact in dissemination through collaboration and develop scientific outcomes on cross-cutting themes; and to maximise the impact of the scientific outcomes through joint awareness raising targeting the Cities Mission Community of Practice. Objectives include, as outlined in the UP2030 Grant Agreement section on Work Package 6, fostering “collaboration [that] could cover e.g. defining complementary solutions, measures or methodologies, capacity building, networking or dissemination activities (such as webinars, workshops, site visits or publications).”

7.3 Roles and responsibilities: Implementation of the roadmap

This section focuses on outlining the stakeholder landscape (see Figure 1) as well as the roles and responsibilities of the core stakeholders to achieve the key objectives of this roadmap for collaboration. The identified **Core Cluster** who is taking the leading role in the implementation of the roadmap are the consortium members of the three Mission Projects UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value. A secondary “**Exchange**” **Cluster** takes the scope wider to include NZN, the Cities Mission Secretariat, the Mission Adaptation, Smart Cities Marketplace, Scalable Cities, and more.

At the first stage the Project Coordinators and the Work Package Leads will be asked to identify the relevant partners within their consortium for the respective themes identified in this document. The Core Cluster members will collaborate closely with the Exchange Cluster, including NZN and the Cities Mission Secretariat. Building strong collaboration with stakeholders beyond the Cities Mission will ensure integration of the outcomes in broader city strategies. For this reason, the Exchange Cluster includes key stakeholders from the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change (e.g., MIP4Adapt, Pathways to Resilience and other relevant projects) and initiatives such as the Smart Cities Marketplace, and Scalable Cities, etc.

Figure 1. Projects, Initiatives and Missions to Engage as UP2030

7.4 Content of the roadmap

The content of this roadmap is structured in the aforementioned main themes: 1) enhance dissemination and maximise impact for the project outcomes for the cities and identify cross cutting themes across the three Mission Projects and 2) raise awareness and impact of the projects to the Mission.

Figure 2. Primary Focus and Involvement of the Working Groups.

7.4.1 Core Cluster

Involvement: Core Group (UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, Re-Value), Pilot and Follower Cities involved in Core Group Projects

7.4.1.1 Enhance dissemination and impact

Objective:

- Build Synergies among the Core Cluster and with the other groups of stakeholders (Exchange Cluster)
- Collaborate on dissemination
- Identify cross-cutting themes between cluster members/projects
- Foster city exchange on Best Practices.

The main objective for the core group was the development of a working group that identified relevant partners able to enhance the dissemination of project impacts at the cities. In order to maximise the impact of the projects' outcome to the cities it was important to build synergies with all the different levels of stakeholders from the Cities Mission as shown in the Figure 1. As the primary target group of this theme are the cities, it was important for the Core Cluster to have close collaboration with the cities – beneficiaries of the Mission Projects and extend their activities as much as possible reaching the cities that are part of the NZC programme.

Some of the potential methods for engaging with these cities included joint participation at Mission events, awareness-raising webinars, and shared communication activities using digital channels. The NZC platform also served as a key space for sharing and communicating project outcomes, particularly towards the final phase of the project, when results and deliverables were made accessible to the wider Mission community.

UP2030 held **regular operational Cluster Meetings with the projects within the same cluster** Re-Value and CLIMABOROUGH to plan collaboration activities – with meetings every 3 months as an initial goal (meetings took place roughly every month finally). This built on and expanded existing exchange meetings that occurred on an ad hoc basis, as per the Project Officer's request, which occurred on the following dates:

- February 2023
- March 2023
- June 2023
- January 2024

To kick off clustering and discuss this Roadmap, an initiating meeting with Re-Value and CLIMABOROUGH took place:

- May 2024

This Core Cluster collaboration operated efficiently through regular coordination meetings rather than formal working groups (as initially anticipated). The originally proposed structure of a rotating co-chair (involving a city representative with ICLEI support) was not implemented, as partners agreed that the established coordination format already ensured effective communication and planning.

Among the three Cluster Projects, simultaneous presence at key events was coordinated to strengthen collaboration and increase visibility within the Cities Mission framework. This included the pitching of joint sessions, shared Marketplace stands and the promotion of project results under a unified Urban Planning and Design Cluster identity. Cluster Project partners were invited to major Mission events to share finalised results and lessons learned. A dedicated session at European Urban Resilience Forum (EURESFO) 2023 in Cascais, Portugal, titled Integrated Climate-Neutral and Resilient Cities: Exploring Innovative Urban Planning and Design Practices, marked the first coordinated presence of the Cluster. This was followed by a shared Marketplace stand at EURESFO 2024 in Valencia, Spain, which further strengthened visibility and cooperation among the three projects. The collaboration continued with a

joint stand and World Café session at the Cities Mission Conference 2025 in Vilnius, Lithuania, and participation in the UP2030 Final Event 2025 in Barcelona, where CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value contributed to thematic sessions, sharing city experiences and insights on lessons supporting climate-neutral urban transitions.

Regular cluster meetings were held approximately every month to review progress, align dissemination activities and plan joint participation at events. These meetings ensured a continuous collaboration among UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value.

Core Cluster meetings held:

- May 2024
- June 2024
- November 2024
- January 2025
- February 2025 (two meetings)
- March 2025
- April 2025 (three meetings)
- May 2025
- June 2025
- July 2025
- September 2025
- October 2025
- November 2025

Additionally, a Community of Practice structure was applied to this collaboration, in the realm of knowledge exchange – with the goal of meeting regularly, either as a stand-alone session or as part of the activities mentioned above. To engage the projects' cities, presentations and exchange sessions among pilot and follower cities were organised. For example, Re-Value's "Re-Value Rounds" series (January-May 2025) involved UP2030 and CLIMABOROUGH partners and gathered around 30-40 participants per session. Similarly, CLIMABOROUGH's "CLIMAWebinars" (e.g. April 2025 session on innovative procurement) and UP2030's thematic webinars (May and October 2025) provided platforms for shared learning and discussion on urban planning, governance and ethics. These exchanges reinforced collaboration and mutual learning among cities involved in the three projects.

UP2030 communication channels (e.g. newsletters, social media) along with those of CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value were actively used to cross-promote events, calls for action, and project outputs. The Informed Cities newsletter, led by Re-Value and managed by ICLEI, regularly featured updates from the Core Cluster, contributing to the joint dissemination strategy.

This objective mainly targeted the core stakeholders from the cluster projects. UP2030 and its sister projects identified shared thematic priorities such as urban governance, citizen engagement, data management and climate-neutral planning and explored opportunities for joint communication products and policy recommendations.

Internally, the cluster projects also coordinated with NZC to ensure alignment of related Work Package activities. These exchanges facilitated the coordination of initiatives and discussions around potential joint outputs, such as policy briefs, shared event contributions and collaborative publications that reflect the collective lessons and experiences of the Urban Planning and Design Cluster.

7.4.1.2 Define cross-cutting themes

Objective:

- Define cross-cutting themes
- Explore opportunities for outputs related to cross-cutting themes (e.g. policy recommendations)

This objective primarily targeted the core stakeholders from the cluster projects. UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value worked together to identify common themes shared across their activities and outputs. These included urban governance and planning, citizen engagement, data management and ethics and innovative approaches to climate-neutral transitions.

Synergies were identified across all levels of the stakeholder landscape, involving project coordinators, work package leaders and representatives from NZC. Discussions during Core Cluster meetings and joint events helped align the thematic focus areas and highlight opportunities for shared outputs and learning (e.g., policy recommendations, shared communication materials, contributions to Mission events).

Common themes such as citizen engagement in urban transition planning, data-informed decision-making and procurement as a driver of innovation were reflected in joint sessions held during EURESFO 2024, the Cities Mission Conference 2025 and the UP2030 Final Event.

7.4.1.3 Interaction with Exchange Cluster

The Core Cluster worked in close collaboration with members of the Exchange Cluster (see section below), including NZC, to define synergies and align project results in support of cities developing their transition pathways towards climate neutrality (e.g. Climate City Contracts). This collaboration also enabled cities involved in the cluster projects to share their experiences and lessons learned within the wider Cities Mission community.

Activities under this collaboration included the **sharing and dissemination of project outcomes, deliverables and resources through the NZC Portal**, reaching not only to Mission Cities but other users of the Portal. As part of *D6.12 Sharing UP2030 best practices and policy briefs with the Mission's platform*, project outputs and resources from UP2030 were shared to the NZC Portal, which functions as the main repository for Mission-related knowledge and tools.

The **Cities Mission Secretariat were regularly informed of the progress** of synergies and as well as the lessons learned and the key outcomes from this collaboration with the cluster projects and the NZC.

Synergies were also explored with other relevant initiatives to the cluster projects and the Cities Mission, including the Smart Cities Marketplace and the Scalable Cities Initiative. These exchanges helped connect cluster activities with broader EU frameworks that support cities in upscaling or replicating successful approaches.

Beyond the Cities Mission, UP2030 and its cluster partners also **engaged with other EU Missions, in particular the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and related initiatives**. This collaboration enabled the identification of shared learning opportunities between cities engaged in both Missions (e.g. Rotterdam, Thessaloniki), allowing cities to develop a holistic approach to climate neutrality and urban resilience, while enabling other cities to learn from their peers.

Core Cluster: Action Points in Summary
<p>Within Core Cluster</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular operational Cluster meetings (e.g. every 3 months) • Identify cross-cutting outcomes of interest • Simultaneous presence at two or more events <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EURESFO 2023, EURESFO 2024, Cities Mission Conference 2025, UP2030 Final Event 2025 • Invitation to UP2030 final conference of Core Cluster projects • Cross-promotion of events and relevant news through Core Cluster project channels • Establishment of Community of Practice: Convene presentations, exchange sessions among pilot and follower cities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Collaborated during Re-Value Rounds (Jan-May 2025) and CLIMAWebinars event series (Apr 2025) ○ Participation in UP2030 thematic webinars (May and Oct 2025) • Explore possible common research outcomes or outputs (e.g. policy recommendations) <p>Interaction with Exchange Cluster</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing and dissemination of project outcomes, deliverables and resources on the NZC Portal • Explore synergies with other relevant initiatives to the cluster projects and the Cities Mission • Seek collaboration with the other Missions, especially the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change

7.4.2 Exchange Cluster

Involvement: Wider Group (Core Group of UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, RE-VALUE alongside Mission on Adaptation and associated projects, Relevant Initiatives, Cities Mission Secretariat)

7.4.2.1 Raise awareness/impact of the projects in the Cities Mission

Objective:

- Joint dissemination activities and knowledge exchange

Joint dissemination activities were carried out in coordination with the Cities Mission, the NZC Platform, and related Mission projects, including sister projects – it was identified suitable opportunities, channels and events to jointly promote project activities and results.

Dissemination opportunities were surveyed identified through regular coordination meetings and ongoing exchanges with NZC and the Mission Secretariat. The projects collaborated to ensure that information about milestones, results and events was shared through Mission channels, newsletters and at major Mission gatherings.

To support this, partners shared a selection of tools, methodologies and knowledge resources developed within UP2030 through the NZC Portal. This ensured their availability to Mission cities and stakeholders. These materials effectively fulfilled the role of the originally envisioned “dissemination packages,” helping transfer tangible results and lessons learned to the broader Cities Mission community.

These joint efforts strengthened the visibility and impact of the Core Cluster within the Cities Mission, improved alignment with the NZC Platform and related initiatives and facilitated the long-term accessibility of project outcomes through “D6.12 – *Sharing UP2030 best practices and policy briefs with the Mission’s platform*”.

Exchange Cluster Activities

- Identify opportunities and channels/events for joint dissemination alongside Cities Mission, NZC and related Mission projects
- Survey key project milestones suited to joint dissemination and create dissemination packages to be shared with Exchange Cluster members
 - Participated in major Mission and EU events, including the NZC Annual Conferences (2023 & 2024) and the Smart City Expo World Congress 2023, to promote cluster results and collaboration.
 - Shared UP2030 tools, methodologies and policy resources through the NZC Portal, ensuring long-term accessibility for Mission cities and stakeholders.

7.5 Documentation of the clustering activities

All activities carried out for the implementation of this roadmap were systematically recorded, ensuring transparency and traceability throughout the process. Data and information management followed the principles established in the UP2030 Data Management Plan.

A rolling document was maintained to register the meetings between the members of the Core Cluster group, including detailed minutes that captured discussions, agreed tasks and next steps. This document was stored in the project's SharePoint repository, ensuring accessibility for all relevant partners.

For collaborative activities aimed at identifying cluster topics and coordinating joint actions, interactive digital tools such as Miro Boards and online document-sharing platforms were used to facilitate remote and participatory work. Images, notes and survey results generated through these tools were collected and archived within the same repository. All materials were documented in an organised and traceable way.